

Stochasticity in Newton's Second Law, Special Relativity and Quantum Mechanics

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Newton's law $F = dp/dt$ is considered to be associated with deterministic kinematics. The problem, we argue, is that dt is not really zero (only very small on Newtonian scales). If, for the sake of argument, one considers a finite dt , one must then consider the workings of force in a very tiny time and there is no reason to believe this is a deterministic situation. It is more likely that there is some stochasticity at the level of dt and dx and so t and x within dt and dx are stochastic and associated with probability. On Newtonian scales, this would not be noticed, but on other scales (quantum ones), it could be.

A key point seems to be that even if one has $x=vt$ (a deterministic equation), one does not really know the x and t values exactly, there is a stochastic uncertainty of dt , dx (because the particle was put in motion by an interaction). This means that even a free particle should have this inherent stochasticity in x and t , even if p and E are considered exact. Now expressions for p and E formally follow from special relativity and so if there is some dx, dt stochasticity and it has a certain range (i.e. a maximum value for dx and dt in a sense), this range should appear in special relativity as one must know dx, dt and dx', dt' .

We have suggested in previous notes that possible dx, dt ranges in fact appear in the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ because for x, t (center of mass description) yielding a certain. Values, off center-of-mass values, $x_1 = x + \hbar/p$ and $t_1 = t + \hbar/E$ also yield the same A . We suggest that these are the "maximum" dx and dt values with uncertainty because the momentum or energy interaction can occur with probability within dx and dt and need not occur at the center-of-mass. It is dx and dt which differ in different frames, e.g. \hbar/p' and \hbar/E' , but there is uncertainty in these ranges, i.e. a probability distribution. This uncertainty is associated with a free particle and should manifest itself in an interaction (e.g. 2-slit interference), but it also means that two body elastic scattering cannot ever be considered fully deterministic. There is still the stochastic, uncertain dx, dt . If one wishes to consider conservation of energy and momentum, however, one uses the notion of a free particle $x=vt$. Even though actual interaction hits may occur at different places, if one has two particles $P(p_1, x_1) P(p_2, x_2)$ in an AND situation, one must have $x_1 = x_2$ in order to show that momentum is conserved at the same x . This leads to the notion of $\exp(ipx)$ as a probability, or more fully $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ which is consistent with the special relativistic condition on the range of dx and dt . If one were to consider special relativity, then two particles together have $E_1 + E_2$ and $p_1 + p_2$ and one uses the same x and t and so $dx = \hbar/(p_1 + p_2)$ and $dt = \hbar/(E_1 + E_2)$. This matches the $P(p_1, x)P(p_2, x)$ scheme for ranges of dx and dt . Alternatively, one may consider that one has a uniform distribution for any outcomes of E_1, E_2, p_1, p_2 elastic scattering which conserve energy and momentum. This leads to $\exp(iC_1E)$ and $\exp(iC_2p)$, but these must display the dt, dx ranges and so one has $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$ in order to have a Lorentz invariant probability.

The above arguments have been based on Newton's second law $dp/dt = F$ and special relativity which means that the two must exist together, which in fact they do. In particular, special relativity is not simply about viewing particles from different frames, but must also be linked with interactions which create the equivalent motion. As shown in (1), one may start with number and

vector concepts E, p without knowing their explicit forms and then use special relativity to calculate them. In (1), however, this involved the notion of $dp = F dt$ and $dke = F dx$ even for the form of p unknown. Thus, $dp/dt = F$ and special relativity are directly intertwined and the notion of a finite stochastic dt and hence dx in $dp/dt = F$ should have effects on special relativity. One, however, has to directly impose this stochasticity in dt (and hence dx) on $dp/dt = F$ by arguing that dt has a finite value with probabilistic t value within and so one must also look for the stochastic dx and dt range in special relativity, i.e. by considering $A = -Et + px$ as described above. The stochasticity is an assumption, but the finite dt and $t + \hbar/E$, $x + \hbar/p$ are not.

Stochasticity and Newton's Second Law

Given Newton's second law:

$$dp/dt = F \quad ((1))$$

we have argued in previous notes that $dt \rightarrow 0$ is a mathematical idealization. dt is finite, albeit very small in the Newtonian world. Here we postulate that not only is dt finite, but that there is stochasticity involved in an interaction, i.e. it cannot be deterministic at every scale. dt then is a kind of maximum range. If dt is a maximum range on the stochasticity of t , then there should also be stochasticity in x and a dx value. These values hold in a particular frame, and so special relativistic equations should allow one to find dx' , dt' in another frame.

Special Relativity and dp/dt

In the above section, we introduced dt as a finite maximum range on stochasticity linked to t and a similar dx based on $dp/dt = F$. We then considered the dt and dx values in different frames and argued that special relativity should govern these.

In this section we wish to point out that there is a strong connection between $F = dp/dt$ and special relativity, i.e. special relativity is about more than frames moving relative to each other. In (1), we argued that special relativity follows from the consideration of a number and vector. For the spatial part, the number is t and the vector r . If one does not know Newtonian mechanics at all (as assumed in (1)), one still knows that a push or pull (force) can set an object in motion. This is the same motion that is seen from a moving frame. This means there must be a link between what is seen in a moving frame and an equation involving force. In (1), we argued that one may postulate a vector quantity p (without knowing its form) such that $dp/dt = F$ holds where F is linked to the push or pull. This means that $dp = F dt$ which may be seen as a physical impulse. In other words, $F dt$ measures the hit of F against a piece of glass as well as the hit against a ball at rest. p should be proportional to the vector v . To create the required number linked to p , one may use $F \cdot dr = (dp/dt) \cdot dr \rightarrow F \cdot dr = dp/dt \cdot v dt = dp \cdot v$. One may then go on to create special relativity such that it acts on both (r vector, ct) and (pc vector, number) (number linked to m_0 and $F \cdot dr$). In (1), we showed that given these two pieces one may obtain the Lorentz matrix and apply it to both (r, ct) and (pc, E). Thus, $dp/dt = F$ is

directly linked to special relativity and if dt is considered a maximum range for stochasticity in t , one needs to consider dt' in another frame as well as dx' .

Considering dx, dt in Special Relativity

Given

$$-E'E' + p'c \cdot p'c = -m_0 c^2 \quad \text{and} \quad -cct't' + r' \cdot r' = -cctt \quad (x=0) \quad ((2))$$

one may see that x', t' are not present in the first equation, but appear in the second. If one considers the RHS of the second equation, then $t \rightarrow t+dt$ simply leads to a new time t_1 . In other words, one would not necessarily examine the second equation of ((2)) to find dx', dt' . If, however, one examines:

$$A = -Et + px \quad ((3))$$

where x, t are part of $x=vt$ describing the center-of-mass, then:

$$t_1 = t + \hbar/E \quad \text{and} \quad x_1 = x + \hbar/p \quad \text{leave } A \text{ unchanged} \quad ((4))$$

One may postulate $dx = \hbar/p$ and $dt = \hbar/E$ as maximum ranges which are not part of $x=vt$, but could still represent x_1, t_1 points of interaction due to the stochasticity which follows from finite dt in $dp/dt = F$. Then ((4)) gives a recipe for how these maximum dx, dt values change in different frames. Within dx, dt in any frame one has stochasticity. So far, we have only discussed the dx, dt values, but how does one find that actual probability linked to these $dx = \hbar/p$ and $dt = \hbar/E$ values?

Two Body Elastic Scattering

If finite dt in $dp/dt = F$ means that one cannot ever deterministically predict the action of F at all scales, then there must be uncertainty in two body elastic scattering. In particular, given an E_1, E_2 and p_1, p_2 (one dimension for simplicity), one cannot argue with certainty that a certain E_3, E_4 and p_3, p_4 will result. If there is uncertainty, then various E_i, E_j and p_i, p_j (vectors) pairs may exist and one might postulate that these all have the same probability. This is the simplest assumption, i.e. a uniform distribution. In such a case, one would then require:

$$P(E) = \exp(i C_1 E) \quad \text{and} \quad P(p) = \exp(i C_2 p) \quad ((5))$$

In the above section, however, we argued that $dt = \hbar/E$ and $dx = \hbar/p$ and so these maximum ranges must be built into ((5)). Furthermore, ((5)) should be continuous functions which leads to the Lorentz invariant result:

$$\exp(-iEt + ipx) \quad ((5))$$

Thus, one may use a physical example, uncertainty from $dp/dt=F$ and special relativity to obtain the quantum mechanical free particle probability, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that free particle quantum mechanics has its starting point in $dp/dt=F$. In particular, we argue that dt must be finite and postulate that it has some maximum value and that there is stochasticity of t 's within and that this implies the same for dx . In other words, at some tiny scale a force interaction is not deterministic. This means that one should find dt , dx and the probabilities.

We first note that $dp/dt=F$ is closely related to special relativity. Furthermore, dx , dt in one frame should become dx' , dt' in another. One should then search for dt and dx in special relativistic equations. We suggest that $A = -Et+px$ implies that $dt=\hbar/E$ and $dx=\hbar/p$ added to t and x leave A unchanged. We postulate that these might be the uncertainty ranges dx and dt . The probabilities are then obtained by considering conservation of energy/momentum and a uniform distribution in 2-body elastic scattering. If dt and dx exist and there is stochasticity, then one cannot deterministically predict the outcome of E_1, E_2, p_1, p_2 . If one assumes a uniform distribution for any outcomes which conserve energy and momentum, then one has $\exp(iC_1E)$ and $\exp(iC_2p)$ as there is no real weight for free particles. This result, however, must predict the ranges $dx=\hbar/p$ and $dt=\hbar/E$ from special relativity, so one should have $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$, we argue.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Special Relativity Based on Frames, but Also Vector and Scalar Interaction Quantities (preprint, zenodo, 2026)